

A case of of craniorachischisis totalis

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Objective

We present a case of Craniorachischisis totalis, which is a very rare congenital anomaly and the most severe form of neural tube defect, presents with anencephaly and total spina bifida.

Methods

Case report.

Results

The male fetus, of a 25 year-old gravida 1para. A termination of pregnancy was performed.

Conclusion

It is important to prevent risk of NTD recurrence in subsequent pregnancies. Supplementation with folic acid is one of the most significant preventative interventions available before conception and during organogenesis. Women at high risk of NTD should take a dose of 5 mg/day until 12 weeks of pregnancy.